

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

German farmers experiences and interest to use different methods to improve soil quality

Farmers perceptions of soil quality are of high importance in the development of more sustainable farming practices. The farmer survey implemented in SoildiverAgro identified relevant soil related agri-environmental problems in the present production as well as the most effective farming practices to face these problems. The survey data was collected from six different regions of Europe. In Germany 200 farmers provided survey answers. Of them 91 % were conventional farmers and 9% organic. With a survey measure we aimed to understand farmers current and prospective adoption of soil management practices on their farms. In Germany among the 13 practices assessed, the most popular was incorporation of crop residue

in the a field (97% of farmers intended to use the practice) and intercropping (87%). Also catchcrops were interesting as 80% of farmers intended to use them, in future. Long rotation periods, less frequent ploughing and reduced tillage depth were adopted by over 70% of farmers. Also, farmers perceptions of the possible impacts of different practices was measured. Especially covering field with organic matter, incorporation of crop residue, intercropping and catch crops were seen as practices that contribute to good soil quality. The overall attitude towards improving soil quality was rather positive in Germany 4,3 on the scale from one to five. The attitude was equal to the average of other countries in the study.

1. Healthy soil as the basis for stable yields.

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KEYWORDS

Soil quality, soil management practices, catch crops

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